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A Proposed Strategy for Activating E-Governance in Educational Institutions and Its Impact on Achieving Competitive Advantage

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Abstract

This study aimed to develop a proposed strategy to activate e-governance in pre-university education institutions and examine its impact on achieving a competitive advantage. The study began by diagnosing the reality of the use of e-governance tools in these institutions, analyzing the shortcomings that hinder the effectiveness of digital transformation, and then designing a strategy based on scientific and practical foundations to activate e-governance, contributing to improving the quality of institutional performance and enhancing its competitiveness. The study used a descriptive-analytical approach, employing various tools to collect data, most notably a questionnaire. The results revealed a noticeable weakness in the implementation of e-governance and limited use of digital tools, which negatively impacted transparency, service quality, and decision-making efficiency. The results also demonstrated that implementing the proposed strategy would contribute to improving administrative and educational performance and achieving a higher degree of excellence and competitiveness within educational institutions. In light of this, the study recommended the need to support digital infrastructure, train human resources, and adopt policies and legislation that support digital transformation in pre-university education.

Keywords: e-governance - competitive advantage.

Introduction:

The current era is witnessing many rapid transformations and changes due to tremendous technological and scientific progress. Educational institutions, in particular, have witnessed many changes. These changes are no longer merely a routine process aimed at interpreting the educational administrative process according to rigid instructions and rules, such as supervising educational institutions, recording the absence and attendance of employees and teachers, maintaining buildings and their equipment, and distributing curricula. Rather, the focus of work has become providing the capabilities that facilitate the comprehensive and integrated growth of learners and prepare them to assume their responsibilities in their future lives. Therefore, leaders must rise to the challenges presented to them in order to achieve a competitive advantage in educational institutions. In light of these challenges and changes, a transformation in the leadership methods of educational institutions is required, shifting from traditional methods to modern ones. One of the most recent of these methods is governance, which seeks to achieve transparency, integrity, oversight, justice, and participation in decision-making. (Al-Zatma, 2016, p. 4)

Governance refers to a set of rules and procedures based on integrity, transparency, accountability, combating corruption, achieving justice without discrimination, and applying the law to all, with effective internal and external oversight.

(Abu Al-Nasr, 2015, 45)

Governance can be defined as a system whereby institutional activities are subject to a set of laws, regulations, and decisions aimed at achieving quality and excellence in performance by selecting appropriate and effective methods to achieve the institution's plans and objectives and controlling relationships between key stakeholders that influence business performance. In other words, we can say that governance is a set of foundations, rules, and procedures followed to ensure transparency, justice, and efficiency among the various categories of people associated with the institution at all levels. <https://www.alyaum.com/articles/6358614>

In light of the technological and electronic revolution that contemporary societies have witnessed and are witnessing, which has imposed itself on all sectors, most countries, their governments, and governmental institutions have begun to transition to cyberspace to provide their services online using various modern technological means, more quickly and at a lower cost, and in a manner that achieves the concepts of justice, equality, transparency, participation, and the implementation of laws and regulations. With the accelerating trend toward reliance on information and communications technology and the transition to electronic organizations, the trend toward adopting the concepts of electronic governance has become one of the fundamental approaches to developing government administration. This trend is known as "e-governance."

<https://egovernancezinab.wordpress.com/author/zinaabdall.a>

Competitive advantage is currently one of the most important mechanisms that help achieve the vision, mission, and goals of educational institutions. Today, almost no global institution or organization lacks distinctive procedures and activities that enable it to compete locally and strive for global competition as well. Institutions are keen to provide the requirements for their stability and growth as a basis for implementing their plans and achieving their goals. What can be relied upon to distinguish educational institutions, whether on a global or local scale, is to define their identity in light of the goals the institution seeks to achieve with distinction. (Ajlan, 2008, 64)

The concept of competitive advantage has gained significant importance in the contemporary era, due to the fact that educational institutions live in environments characterized by rapid change and complexity, and characterized by various phenomena such as globalization, changing customer demands, increasing competition for products, and the revolution in information and communications technology. Based on the strategic plan for pre-university education (2014-2030), which aims to prepare and develop leaders in educational and administrative work, and to focus on the distinguished and competent preparation of school principals as leaders who possess administrative, technical, and technological capabilities through a system that supports empowerment, to achieve this strategy, the Ministry of Education has adopted policies for reform and improvement that are consistent with the United Nations Charter on Human Rights. The most important of these policies is strengthening the institutional structure in schools and building the capacity of workers to implement decentralization in a manner that ensures good governance.

(Egyptian Ministry of Education, 2014, 2-3).

Competitiveness has indicated the sustainable professional development of workers, and competitive advantage has become one of the options that institutions resort to in order to confront all that is new. Educational institutions seek, in a highly competitive

environment, to add value to human resources and achieve excellence and creativity by investing the intellectual, mental, and creative energy of these human resources.

First: The research problem and its questions:

Governance systems have recently become a cornerstone for implementing quality assurance standards and a axis upon which educational reform processes around the world are based. This is achieved through a set of integrated and interactive human and material elements that create harmony and balance within the educational institution. This is achieved through the implementation of a set of systems, laws, and instructions aimed at achieving quality and excellence in the outcomes of academic and administrative staff. This is achieved through the selection of appropriate strategies to achieve the goals of the educational institution.

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Despite the Ministry of Education's commitment to achieving competitiveness, quality, and excellence in institutional performance through the implementation of the standards set by the National Authority for Quality Assurance and Accreditation of Education, foremost among which are leadership and governance standards as a primary determinant of educational quality, attempts to develop schools have not achieved their expected results. This is due to the lack of a complete understanding of the concepts of institutional governance, reform approaches, and strategic visions for continuous development and improvement processes among leaders, staff, and teachers in educational institutions.

(Maher Ahmed, 2015, pp. 262-330)

Despite the efforts made by the Ministry of Education to achieve a competitive advantage in primary schools in Egypt, these efforts and attempts have not been able to achieve competitiveness due to shortcomings in the good governance of educational institutions. These shortcomings include a low level of awareness of the concepts of good governance and good management, self-monitoring, the absence of principles related to transparency, accountability, and accountability, limited financial resources, and the participation of stakeholders in school decision-making through community dialogue.

(Dahawi and Al-Mullaji, 2010, 43-44)

It is clear from the above that, despite the efforts made at the official level to implement the principles of e-governance in educational institutions, there are some problems that stand in the way of their intended implementation. Hence, the problem of this study arose, which concerns developing a proposed strategy for implementing the principles of e-governance in primary schools in the North Sinai Governorate, as a model for pre-university education institutions, given that they are affected by the variables of the external environment that influence all educational institutions. Although each educational institution has an independent identity imposed by its own internal and external environmental conditions and factors, it faces the same challenges as most educational institutions and is affected by the same available opportunities and threats affecting the external environment of Egyptian society as a whole. The recent COVID-19 pandemic crisis has revealed the importance of e-governance in providing essential services to citizens, such as remote education monitoring, as well as innovative methods for crisis management. This is achieved through the application of e-governance principles in educational institutions and its role in achieving a competitive advantage. In light of the above, the study problem is determined and lies in the following main question:

What is the proposed strategy for implementing e-governance in educational institutions, and its impact on achieving competitive advantage?

The following sub-questions arise from the previous main question:

1. What is the conceptual framework for e-governance? What are its dimensions and requirements for its implementation, especially in educational institutions?
2. What are the theoretical foundations for competitive advantage in educational institutions, and what are the requirements for achieving it?
3. What is the reality of implementing e-governance in educational institutions in North Sinai Governorate, and its impact on achieving competitive advantage?
4. How can a proposed strategy be developed to implement the principles of e-governance in educational institutions, and its impact on achieving competitive advantage?

Second: Study Objectives

By answering the previous questions, this study aims to:

1. Identify the conceptual framework of e-governance, its dimensions, and the requirements for its implementation, especially in educational institutions.
2. Identify the theoretical foundations of competitive advantage in educational institutions and the requirements for achieving it.
3. Identify the reality of implementing e-governance in educational institutions in North Sinai Governorate, and its impact on achieving competitive advantage.
4. Developing a proposed strategy to activate the principles of e-governance in pre-university education institutions, and its impact on achieving a competitive advantage.

Third: The Importance of the Study

This study relates to the concept of e-governance, which is considered one of the most important concepts in recent times. This stems from a belief in its importance in achieving success for institutions in general, and educational institutions in particular. E-governance is not a spontaneous process that occurs at any time or in any element of the educational process. Rather, it is an organized process that requires the leaders of pre-university education institutions to be aware of the principles of good governance and to master the principles of its electronic application, based on their belief in the effective role it plays in achieving a competitive advantage.

Hence, this study examines the reality of e-governance in pre-university education institutions in North Sinai. The researcher believes that this study will have a significant impact on achieving competitiveness among the governorate's schools and raising their efficiency. Its importance stems from the importance of the variables it addresses, which are as follows:

1. It addresses an important approach among the most recent advanced administrative approaches, namely e-governance, in light of the tremendous technological progress witnessed in the twenty-first century. It also addresses the ability of educational institutions' administrations to keep pace with these technological developments in line with the requirements of the age of technology and digitization, and the extent of its application in primary schools in North Sinai.

2. The governorate's primary schools need such studies to help achieve competitiveness among pre-university education institutions.
3. Although there are many differences regarding the concept of governance, there is near consensus that its implementation enhances the efficiency of any institution, achieves competitiveness with other institutions, and supports its ability to deal with crises. The COVID-19 crisis has revealed the importance of e-governance in achieving competitiveness among pre-university education institutions.
4. The topic of e-governance and its role in achieving competitiveness among pre-university education institutions is a new topic that suffers from a lack of field and practical studies. Therefore, this study is expected to provide an additional reference in this field.
5. The proposed strategy presented by the study can help those responsible for pre-university education institutions determine the procedures and requirements necessary for this, thus paving the way for achieving educational competitiveness.

Fourth: Study Methodology and Tools

Based on the nature of the study and the information sought to understand the reality of e-governance in pre-university educational institutions in general and primary schools in North Sinai in particular, and its role in achieving competitiveness, the researcher used the descriptive approach, which is useful in this type of study. This approach focuses on accurately describing the phenomenon to be studied as it exists in reality, expressing it qualitatively and quantitatively. (Obeidat et al., 2008, p. 23)

The qualitative approach describes the phenomenon and clarifies its characteristics. The quantitative approach provides a numerical description that illustrates the magnitude or size of the phenomenon and the degree of its correlation with other phenomena. This is done through understanding the concept of e-governance, the requirements for its implementation, and its role in achieving competitiveness. Then, the most important obstacles to the implementation of e-governance are identified. The study relies on a questionnaire as a tool, which is directed to a sample of officials in charge of pre-university education institutions in North Sinai's educational directorates and administrations, and those in charge of primary schools in the first and second cycles, with the aim of identifying the extent of e-governance implementation, its role in achieving competitiveness among schools, and identifying the obstacles that may prevent its activation, while presenting a proposed strategy to activate the role of e-governance in improving competitiveness in pre-university education institutions in North Sinai.

Fifth: Study Limits

In line with the study objectives, the following limitations were focused on:

1. The objective limit: This study was limited to understanding the reality of e-governance among officials in charge of pre-university education institutions in the directorates, administrations, and primary education schools in North Sinai Governorate, and its role in achieving competitiveness.
2. The institutional limit: This study was limited to the Education Directorate, the Arish Education Administration, and primary education schools in North Sinai Governorate.

3. The human limit: This study is applied to some officials in charge of pre-university education institutions in the directorates, administrations, and primary education schools in North Sinai Governorate.
4. The time limit: The study is expected to be conducted during the academic year 2023-2024.

Sixth: Study Terminology

1. Strategy:

A strategy is defined as the approach used in implementation, emanating from a clear and comprehensive vision through which strategic objectives are achieved. It works to identify and evaluate various methods that achieve the organization's goals and mission, and then select the best of these methods. (Hilal, 2008, p. 11)

The researcher defines it procedurally as a decision made by an institution to improve its performance using available resources and capabilities.

2. Governance

It is the system through which institutions are managed and their operations are controlled, including systems that govern the relationships between the key stakeholders that influence performance. It also includes the elements of strengthening the institution in the long term and identifying those responsible, within a framework of participation, justice, transparency, and accountability. Through the governance of their operations, institutions seek to ensure consistency among their various administrative units, so that the work of these units complements one another, leading to the achievement of their goals and excellence.

(Al-Dahshan, 2020)

The current study defines it as a system implemented pursuant to a set of laws, regulations, and decisions aimed at achieving the institution's plans and objectives to achieve quality and excellence in performance.

3. E-Governance

It is the governance that works to use information and communications technology to improve and strengthen the foundations of governance and management, develop the structure of educational institutions, and connect universities to advance the educational environment. (Al-Dahshan, 2020)

The current study defines e-governance as a virtual system that enables administrative bodies to direct the work of pre-university education institutions, fulfill their obligations to beneficiaries, and monitor the quality of performance using advanced technologies that support electronic transparency, electronic accountability, electronic participation, and electronic independence, thus enhancing the competitive advantage of pre-university education institutions.

4. Competitiveness:

The goal sought to achieve superiority over competitors, through the optimal use of material, human, and technological resources to carry out its activities skillfully, with the greatest efficiency, and at the lowest cost, in a manner that achieves diverse benefits and added value to its outputs relative to its competitors, within conditions and a climate conducive to competition and uniqueness. (Haiba, 2019, p. 188)

Porter believes that competitive advantage is the new methods discovered by an organization that are more effective than those used by competitors. This enables the organization to embody this discovery in the field. In other words, it creates a process of innovation within the organization in its broadest sense, meaning the organization's ability to provide a service at a lower cost and a product that is distinct from its counterparts in the market, while maintaining this capability. (Michael E. Porter, 2006, 4)

The researcher defines it operationally as the goal sought by pre-university educational institutions to achieve excellence, through the optimal use of material, human, and technological resources to carry out their activities with skill and at the lowest cost, in a way that achieves added value to their outputs relative to their competitors.

Seventh: Previous Studies

The topic of governance has been presented in more than one field or institution, as a necessity that has imposed itself on all sectors, including the pre-university education sector, as most institutions have begun to move to cyberspace to provide their services and manage their affairs via the internet and various modern technological means, more quickly and at a lower cost. Therefore, this study relies on previous studies that examined e-governance and its role in achieving competitiveness. In this context, the researcher reviews the most important previous studies, both Arab and foreign, that addressed the subject of the study, as follows:

Arab Studies

1. Anwar's study (2021) entitled: "Requirements for Utilizing Competitive Advantage in Basic Education Schools in Egypt in Light of the Excellence Strategy."

The study aimed to identify the most important requirements for utilizing competitive advantage in basic education schools in Egypt in light of the excellence strategy. The study adopted a descriptive approach through a review of theoretical and educational literature. The research sample included basic education school principals and deputies, basic education teachers, and educational quality auditors in the directorate and administrations in Sohag Governorate. The research tool was a questionnaire as a means of obtaining information. The study identified several requirements necessary to achieve competitive advantage in basic education schools, including the necessity of adopting a strategy of excellence and difference in basic education schools, rewarding outstanding performance, and also requirements related to resources, capabilities, and skills. It also required providing learners with distinguished education and educational services, supporting and encouraging teachers to enable them to perform outstandingly according to quality standards, providing a learning environment that supports diversity and creativity, and designing educational activities that enhance creativity and critical thinking for all stakeholders in the educational process.

2. Al-Dahshan's study (2020) entitled: "**A Proposed Vision for the Requirements for Implementing E-Governance at Assiut University in Light of the Fourth Industrial Revolution.**" The study aimed to develop a proposed vision for the requirements for implementing e-governance at Assiut University in light of the Fourth Industrial Revolution. The conceptual framework for e-governance and the concept of the Fourth Industrial Revolution were presented. The researchers used a descriptive approach, relying

on its most important tool, the questionnaire, to identify the opinions of faculty members at some of Assiut University's faculties regarding the reality of implementation and the obstacles that prevent its proper implementation. The questionnaire was administered to a sample of faculty members at Assiut University in some of its theoretical and practical faculties. The study concluded that the reality of implementing e-governance at Assiut University was moderate, based on the average responses of the sample members. The researcher developed a proposed vision for the requirements for implementing e-governance at Assiut University in light of the Fourth Industrial Revolution. The implementation procedures for the vision included a set of axes, namely the objectives of e-governance, political and legal legislation for e-governance, human resources and administrative leadership for e-governance, e-partnership with the production and service sectors, material and financial resources, the regulatory environment for e-governance, and oversight in governance. Electronic, and each axis includes those responsible for implementation, and evidence and proof to achieve the axis. The obstacles to implementing the proposed vision 3h were presented, as well as the guarantees and mechanisms that must be available for the success of the proposed vision.

3. Sharabati's study (2020) entitled: **"Implementing Governance in Education Directorates in Palestine from the Perspectives of School Principals and Administrators: A Field Study in Schools in the Hebron and Bethlehem Governorates."** The study aimed to identify the level of governance implementation in the education directorates in the Hebron and Bethlehem governorates from the perspectives of school principals and administrators. The research team used the descriptive approach in its study, and a stratified random sample was selected at a rate of 30% of the study population (n = 1038), which amounted to (311) principals and administrators. To achieve the study objectives, the researchers constructed a questionnaire to measure the degree of governance application, consisting of 50 paragraphs distributed over five areas. The validity and reliability of the questionnaire were verified using appropriate research methods, while appropriate statistical analyses were used to answer the study questions and examine the hypotheses. The results of the study showed that the degree of governance application in the education directorates in the Hebron and Bethlehem governorates from the point of view of school principals and administrators was average, and that there were no statistically significant differences at the significance level (0.000) between the averages of the study sample's responses to the degree of governance application in the education directorates in the Hebron and Bethlehem governorates attributed to the variable of years of experience, while there were significant differences between the averages of the study sample's responses attributed to the variables of the directorate and job title. In light of the results, the researchers recommended enhancing the degree of governance application in the education directorates in The Hebron and Bethlehem governorates, using all available means, are also conducting specialized studies on educational governance by researchers, educators, and institutions concerned with implementing governance.

Foreign Studies:

1. Kovaris' study (2017) entitled: **"School Discipline. Investment Competitiveness and Mediating Educational"**

aimed to identify the factors that explain global competitiveness in education. It confirms that school discipline and investment in education impact competitiveness as a result of the positive impact on educational performance. More importantly, it draws on

government spending data from the World Bank and the World Economic Forum on competitiveness in education, which is supposed to impact five key dimensions of school discipline: good student listening and noise levels, teacher wait times and students performing well, the academic standards of educational institutions in general, and the subsequent impact on academic performance in reading, mathematics, and science, ultimately impacting competitiveness. The study concluded that school discipline (88%) is of relative importance compared to investment in education (12%) on educational performance, showing that both variables are significantly related to direct competitiveness. From the above, it is clear that competitive advantage is now a strategic and legitimate goal sought by all schools wishing to survive. This goal is achieved through strategic leadership that possesses the skills and capabilities to achieve and enhance it.

2. **Paulo's study (2016)** examines centralized governance and the need to examine official Chinese websites within the framework of e-governance. To obtain high-quality information and e-services that will improve confidence in the implementation of e-governance, the study used a descriptive-analytical approach, and (143) individuals working in business and research were selected. The study concluded that the quality of information improved through transparency and sharing of the provided e-services.

3. **Seddiky's study (2015)** aimed to examine how and to what extent e-governance enhances the quality of education and human resource development. This study was conducted using a qualitative and quantitative research approach based on primary and secondary data. To verify the validity of the research data, a semi-structured questionnaire was used to collect data from respondents through face-to-face interviews. A sample of 120 teachers, students, and officials at Shahjalal University of Science and Technology was selected. The results of the study reveal that, despite some limitations, e-governance contributes significantly to improving the quality of education and developing human skills, making it suitable for the competitive global market. General Comment on Previous Studies

The researcher reviewed the most important previous studies addressing the topic of the current study. She noted that these studies generally focused on highlighting governance in educational institutions and its relationship to achieving competitiveness. The current study is consistent with previous studies in its approach to governance principles in terms of concept, importance, and constraints. This study agreed on the presence of a trend among those responsible for educational development to implement e-governance in educational institutions, as well as its role in achieving competitiveness. The current study differs from previous studies in its focus on examining the reality of e-governance in pre-university educational institutions in North Sinai Governorate, its role in achieving competitiveness, and the presentation of a proposed strategy for implementing e-governance principles. It also differs from previous studies in its study community and timeframe.

Results

The study yielded a set of findings that reflect the reality of e-government implementation in pre-university education institutions prior to the implementation of the proposed strategy. These findings include the following:

1. The weak level of digital transformation within educational institutions, as it was found that the majority of administrative and educational processes are still managed using

traditional methods, with a heavy reliance on paperwork and the absence of integrated electronic systems.

2. Low levels of transparency and accountability, as a result of the absence of electronic systems that contribute to documenting procedures and monitoring performance, leading to limited availability of accurate data necessary for decision-making.
3. Low administrative and organizational efficiency, as institutions suffer from slow processing of transactions, a lack of coordination between administrative units, and a high rate of errors resulting from manual work.
4. Weak communication channels with parents and the local community, in the absence of interactive electronic platforms that contribute to enhancing transparency and activating the community's role in supporting the educational process.
5. Lack of technological training for human resources, as the results showed an urgent need for regular training programs to develop the skills of teachers and administrators in using modern tools and software.
6. The absence of unified digital databases negatively impacts the accuracy and quality of available information, thus hampering planning, monitoring, and evidence-based decision-making.
7. The weak competitiveness of educational institutions, due to their failure to keep pace with technological developments and the poor level of services provided compared to other institutions that have begun their digital transformation.

Based on the findings obtained prior to the implementation of the proposed strategy, a set of recommendations can be presented aimed at improving the reality of e-government in pre-university education institutions and enhancing their competitiveness, as follows:

Recommendations:

1. The necessity of adopting a clear national plan to implement e-government, including well-studied timelines and comprehensive institutional support for implementing digital transformation in pre-university education.
2. Investing in technological infrastructure by providing institutions with modern devices, communication networks, and appropriate software that enable efficient electronic operations.
3. Developing ongoing training programs for educational and administrative staff, aimed at raising digital awareness and developing the technical skills that enable them to interact effectively with e-government systems.
4. Establish electronic platforms for communication with parents and the local community, contributing to enhanced transparency and community participation, and direct monitoring of student performance.
5. Design electronic systems for managing information and databases to ensure accurate data collection, analysis, and use in supporting decision-making and improving the quality of the educational process.
6. Develop a digital oversight system that enables tracking of administrative and educational performance and provides periodic feedback to contribute to improving the quality of services provided.

7. Support a culture of digital transformation within institutions by spreading awareness of the importance of e-government, encouraging innovation, and the use of technological solutions in education and administration.

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